

GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES OF VERBS IN ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION

This article will address the important role of verbs in most languages, at least in such languages as Indo-European, Semitic, and Finno-Ugric, have so many distinctive features that it is absolutely necessary to recognize them as a separate class of words, even if in some cases one or another characteristic feature is absent. This article will also look through the characteristics of the distinction of persons (1st, 2nd and 3rd), tenses, types and mood.

Key words: main verbs, regular verbs, irregular verbs, grammatical categories and characteristics of verbs.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье речь пойдет о важной роли глаголов в большинстве языков, по крайней мере в таких языках, как индоевропейский, семитский и финно-угорский, имеющих так много отличительных черт, что совершенно необходимо выделить их в отдельный класс языков. слов, даже если в ряде случаев тот или иной характерный признак отсутствует. В этой статье также будут рассмотрены характеристики различения лиц (1-го, 2-го и 3-го), времен, типов и наклонений.

Ключевые слова: основные глаголы, правильные глаголы, неправильные глаголы, грамматические категории и характеристики глаголов.

INTRODUCTION

The grammatical categories of the English verb are the subject of numerous works of a general and special nature on the theory and history of the grammatical structure of the English language. Such prominent linguists as Ilyish B.A., Barkhudarov L.S., Smirnitsky and many others were engaged in the study of this problem in detail. The verb in English - both in terms of its specific weight, and in terms of the number and methods of formation of grammatical forms - is certainly the central part of speech. In terms of the number of grammatical forms, the verb has no equal parts of speech in English. When comparing temporal forms, forms of aspect, voice, mood, there are significant discrepancies not only in the volume of these grammatical forms, but also in the very essence of the categories. So, for example, in the Russian language the

aspect category reflects the opposition of the perfect and imperfect aspect, and the English aspect is the opposition of an action lasting in time and an action devoid of a sign of duration, and the presence of categories that are not at all characteristic of the Russian language - perfect, future tense with point of view of the past. All this and much more puts the verb at the forefront of learning English grammar. The verb has a very developed system of temporal forms, the opposition of the active and passive voices, the opposition of the indicative, subjunctive and imperative moods.

These are the main verbal categories covering the entire verb system as a whole. In addition, there are residual, defective forms of face and number; whether they can be classified into categories is a moot point, since they do not represent a systematic series of forms (for example, in the preterit of verbs, with the exception of the verb to be 'to be', these forms are absent altogether). A verb is a part of speech that expresses the grammatical meaning of an action. The grammatical meaning of an action is understood broadly: it is not only an activity in the true sense of the word, but also a state and simply an indication that a given object exists, that it belongs to a certain class of objects. Thus, we can say that the English verb system is usually called the most complex grammatical structure of the language.

METHODS

The purpose of the study is to analyze the use of the categories of the English verb in the context, to show their essence.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set

1. Consider the main grammatical categories of the English verb.
2. Define each category of the English verb.
3. Consider the application of the grammatical categories of the English verb in a specific context.

This course consists of an introduction, a literature review, one chapter, a conclusion, a list of references and an appendix.

As M. Bloch notes: "The category of time is an integral grammatical category, where the personal form of the verb always expresses a temporal distinction. The category of time has different interpretations of various scientists. Thus, in traditional linguistics, grammatical time is often represented in three forms, consisting of a line: past, present and future forms. The future in the past is not included in the scheme based on a linear rule, therefore, this system is considered incomplete, not covering all linguistic information "[4,167-168]

Further, M. Bloch notes: "The voice category occupies a special place in the system of verbal categories, therefore it reflects the process control in relation to the participants and denotes a syntactic construction. The passive form expresses the reception of action on the part of the subject of the syntactic construction; its weak opposite form is the real form has the meaning "non-passivity. Another feature of the English voice is that forms of the active voice often convey the meaning of the passive." [4,170]

"In English, a species can be more accurately defined as a category that conveys the nature of the course of an action in relation to the moment (length) of time indicated by the form. Therefore, the species forms are called species-temporal forms (categories) to emphasize the inseparable connection between the type and time in English" I.P. Ivanova. [8.52]. Mood can be the important grammatical category as it means the attitude of the speaker to the action, expressed by the verb in terms of reality.

Many grammarians list the following moods in English and other languages: indicative, subjunctive, imperative, infinitive, and participle. They are sometimes called fact-mood, thought-mood, and will-mood. However, they do not express the different relationship between "subject and verb" as Sweet says. It would be more correct to say that they express a certain attitude (attitudes of the mind) of the speaker to the content of the sentence, although in some cases the choice of mood is determined not by the attitude of the speaker, but by the nature of the subordinate clause itself and its relationship to the main nexus on which it depends. Further, it is vital to recall that we speak of "inclination" only if the attitude of the speaker is expressed by the form of the verb; therefore, mood is a syntactic, not a conceptual category. A. I. Smirnitsky distinguishes "a) the subjunctive I, which includes statements that do not contradict reality; b) the subjunctive II, on the contrary, implies statements that contradict reality c) presumptive, formed by the combination of should with an infinitive for any subject d) conditional mood - analytical forms with should and would, functioning in the main body of the conditional sentence.

RESULTS

Any verbal form of the English language is either non-perfect or perfect: I wrote - I had written. This applies both to the predicative forms of the verb (in the indicative and subjunctive moods) and to the non-predicative forms. The opposition of perfect and non-perfect forms of the grammatical category of temporal reference. Non-perfect forms express an action or state in itself, unconsciously to any previous or subsequent moment, and, therefore, a non-

perfect form (out of context) does not express any correlation of the action. Perfect forms express the action not in itself, but as correlated with some subsequent moment (or action).

Hence, perfect forms make it possible to present an action, on the one hand, as preceding something, and on the other hand, as connected with the subsequent moment with which it is correlated. Expressing precedence, perfect forms represent an action in the period up to some point, and this may be the precedence of something in the past (Past Perfect), future (Future Perfect) or present; the form (Present Perfect) expresses the precedence not only of the moment of speech, but also of any moment in general, abstractly: He knew where Halivand lived, but had never been there - He knew where Halivand lived, but had never been there.

You have loved her from a child, my friend- You have loved her since childhood, my friend. The relationship of what is reported in the form of the perfect with the subsequent moment can be different. It depends on the lexical meaning of the verb, on the context in general and on the tense form. Usually this is completeness or continuity: People have talked like that from time immemorial - People have been talking this way since time immemorial. By evening a strange quite had settled down on Hanans - In the evening, a strange silence came in Khans.

In the first example, the perfect form expresses the completeness of the process, in the last example - a process that continuously lasted throughout the entire previous period until its final moment; the connection here is expressed as a successive connection between the past and the present. In the Present Perfect form, it is also necessary to take into account the specifics of the Present value. If a verb in its lexical meaning expresses an action that implies a limit beyond which it cannot develop, then such a verb in the perfect form (as well as in the Indefinite form) always expresses the completion of the action: I have come on purpose - I came with a purpose.

The meaning of completeness disappears if the context reveals the action as multiple: Fleur does what she likes - Fleur liked to do what she liked. You have always spoiled her. So, the meaning of perfect forms (correlation with the following) in each individual case of their use is revealed more clearly either as the meaning of precedence in time, or as a connection with the next moment (effectiveness, completeness, succession): "Ten years ago he had been one of the lads with no thought in the world but the girls and the sport results" - "Ten years ago he was one of the boys without any worldly worries, while he was successful

in sports and with girls. "Well, what's changed? Himself? or the world? or both "-
" Yet what has changed? Is he on his own? world? Or both?"

In the first sentence, the temporal meaning of precedence is predominant; in the second - the value of the connection with the subsequent (effectiveness). The difference in the meaning of non-perfect and perfect forms is clearly seen when they are compared: Quite settled over the little community of Stilleveld- Silence covered the small community of Stillveld. By evening a strange quite had settled down on Hanans - In the evening, a strange silence covered Hana. In both examples, the verbs are used in the indicative mood in the past tense. In the first example, the fact of silence is given in itself, without reference to any other subsequent moment, as a simple fact that took place at that moment in the past, which is being narrated (non-perfect form used). In the second example, the same phenomenon (which also took place in the past) is expressed in the form of the perfect: it is presented as taking place over a whole period of time and ending by a certain moment: silence came towards evening, the same process of the onset of silence proceeded in the period of time preceding evening. The meaning of the preceding period is here expressed by the grammatical meaning of the perfect form; the circumstance (by evening) only concretizes this period and emphasizes the significance of the preceding: It had been a hot dusty day. Men were struggling back to their camps after working - It was a hot, dusty day. After work, the men rushed to their camps.

DISCUSSION

Infinitive - "I am glad to see you," said John.

"I am very glad to have seen you again" - I was glad to see you.

In both examples, the speakers express joy over the meeting, however, in the first example, the non-perfect form of the infinitive (to see) is used, since it is enough to express that this place takes place; in the second example, the perfect form (to have seen) is used, since the meeting of friends took place before the described moment, (the interlocutors say goodbye) and, therefore, the speaker expresses his pleasure about the action, which already refers to the elapsed, preceding period of time.

Gerund -being out in a boat on the river Lea soon makes you smart at handling a craft. It dawned upon Andrew, with a pang of disma that his having been in practice in this remote Welsh mining town condemned him.

The first example talks about how useful it is (in general) to ride on the Li River; the action of being out is considered without regard to any previous or subsequent moment; in the second example, how fateful the fact that he had

previously worked in a mining town in Wales (his having been in practice) had for Andrew.

Communion I- and Mrs Payton, having long been a resident of the city and knowing much about the Griffiths, recognized not only the name but the resemblance of Clyde. but Clyde's resemblance to his family.

But I must say, even to you, having known this family from childhood, that you cherish a terrible mistake. - But I must say, even to you, knowing this family from childhood, you make a terrible mistake.

General forms do not give the action any special characteristic. They only state the completion of an action, present it in a general form and, thus, in themselves do not address the issue of its completion or incompleteness; the latter is determined by the lexical meaning of the verb, compatibility with adverbial words and the context as a whole. The specific meaning expressed by these forms is called the "general aspect". The forms of the continued form give the action a special characteristic. They represent the action in its course, movement and, therefore, always express the action still unfinished. The aspect value expressed by these forms is called the "continued aspect".

In the following example, the verb forms are used in the same mood, in the form of the same tense (past indicative); Both forms are imperfect. However, the action itself is presented, "depicted" in time in a completely different way: Tonight the three were dining together. And as they dined Freddy airily remarked... "You're smiling" Alice said. - We had three dinners together tonight. As they were having dinner, Freddie remarked gracefully. You smile, said Alice. The nerve is regenerating - Nerves are regenerating. The first sentence uses the continued form (were dining): three are having lunch together; the action is depicted as an ongoing process. In the second sentence, the general form (dined) is used: the action is also only stated, the author does not need to depict the process in its course.

The species category is also expressed in the infinitive: His intention was to dine and pass the evening playing billiards. - His intention was to have dinner and spend the evening playing billiards.

I happened to be spending a day in Paris.

The aspect category does not apply to all English verbs. It does not have those verbs whose lexical meaning makes their use in the form of the continued form illogical or even absurd, since they cannot express the action in its course, development, in its concrete course. So, these forms are uncharacteristic, for example, for such verbs as to resemble "to remind someone", "to be like

someone", to possess "to possess", to contain "to contain", to belong "to belong", to metter "to mean something", to consist "to consist of something". Such verbs, of course, are used only in the general form, for example: he resembles his father; - he looks like his father, the book contains five chapters; - the book consists of five chapters, he possesses many good qualities. - he has many good qualities. qualities.

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn: According to their generalized lexical meaning, verbs can be characterized as words denoting processes (in the broad sense of the word), and answering the questions "what to do, what to do?". Verbs have grammatical categories of tense (present, past, future), pledge, mood and perform the function of a predicate in a sentence. The grammatical category of time (tense) is the relation of the action to the moment of reference, which is, first of all, the conditional moment of speech. There are three moods in English: indicative, subjunctive and imperative. The grammatical category of the voice shows whether the person or object expressed by the noun or pronoun in the function of the subject, the producer of the action, or whether he himself experiences someone else's action.

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